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The impact of E-beam treatment on the microbial population and sensory quality of hard annatto-coloured cheese

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1 **The impact of E-beam treatment on the microbial population and sensory quality**
2 **of hard annatto-coloured cheese**

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19

20 **Abstract**

21 The effects of E-beam radiation on microbiota, colour, texture and sensorial properties
22 of hard annatto-coloured cheese during storage at 4 and 14°C were studied. Doses of
23 up to 2 kGy provoked a decrease in the total bacterial number, although microbiota
24 recovery to initial levels during storage, even under refrigeration temperature, was
25 observed. However, a higher temperature (14°C) was required to detect bacterial
26 growth in cheese treated at 3 kGy. Moreover, the effects of the dose on the hardness,
27 springiness, cohesiveness and colour parameters were interdependent of the storage
28 conditions. According to the combined effects of E-beam treatment and storage
29 conditions, multivariate cluster analysis allowed treated cheeses irradiated at 0-1 kGy
30 (cluster 1) to be distinguished from those irradiated at 2-3 kGy (cluster 2), which were
31 stored at 4°C for 28 days. Cluster 3 included irradiated cheeses (1-3 kGy) stored at a
32 higher temperature (14°C). Although off-odour and off-flavours arose immediately after
33 treatment, they disappeared progressively during storage at doses lower than 2 kGy.
34 Nevertheless, consumers could detect changes in the colour derived from the radiation
35 at 2 kGy, however, those changes may be unimportant because of the wide colour
36 ranges of commercial annatto-coloured cheeses.

37

38 **Keywords:** E-beam radiation; hard cheese; annatto; microbiota response; sensorial
39 attributes

40

41 1. Introduction

42 Hard cheese varieties are the most produced and consumed in the world, accounting
43 for approximately 45% of the total volume of cheese produced in the EU and the USA,
44 according to official statistics (EC Milk Market Observatory, 2017; USDA-NASS, 2017).
45 Its hygienic quality, however, can be sometimes compromised by the growth of several
46 pathogens (e.g., *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Staphylococcus aureus* or *Escherichia coli*)
47 due to the inadequate management of the storage temperature. This scenario is
48 heightened when whole cheese is transformed into portions, slices or grated since this
49 operation involves additional handlings that increase the risk of contamination with
50 pathogens present in the industrial environment. Moreover, although the long ripening
51 times of hard cheeses yield a microbiologically safe product, since a decrease of the
52 pH and the water activity occurs during ripening (Brooks et al., 2012), they may be
53 launched to the market at an intermediate ripening state. In fact, a prevalence of *L.*
54 *monocytogenes* at a level of 0.2% (n=1242) in hard cheese samples (Little, Sagoo,
55 Gillespie, Grant, & McLauchlin, 2009) has been observed in the UK. Additionally, a
56 contamination with this bacterium prompted a large recall of dry cheese in Canada and
57 the USA in 2017 (CFIA, 2017a; FDA, 2017). Likewise, the survival of *E. coli* O157:H7
58 (Schlesser et al., 2006), *L. monocytogenes* (Ryser, 2007) and *Salmonella* spp. (Wood,
59 Collins-Thompson, Irvine, & Myhr, 1984) in Cheddar cheese after 60 days of ripening
60 has been reported. Even, a *S. Typhimurium* outbreak was linked to the former cheese
61 type after the legally required holding period (D'Aoust, Warburton, & Sewell, 1985).
62 Similar considerations may be made in relation to other hard cheese varieties, e.g.,
63 Swiss cheese (Zweifel et al., 2010) and Comté (CFIA, 2017b).

64 Ionizing irradiation has proven to be an effective non-thermal technology for the
65 sanitation of a variety of foods, mainly to reduce *L. monocytogenes* in several ready-to-
66 eat foods (Cabeza, Cambero, Hoz, & Ordóñez, 2007; Medina et al., 2009). Due to the
67 reported higher radioresistance of *L. monocytogenes* in comparison to *E. coli* O157:H7
68 and *Salmonella* spp. (Mahapatra, Muthukumarappan, & Julson, 2005), researchers

69 have used *L. monocytogenes* as a model in studies directed to obtain a
70 microbiologically safe product via E-beam application. Doses of up to 3 kGy allow
71 control of *L. monocytogenes* in different cheese varieties (Kim et al., 2007; Konteles,
72 Sinanoglou, Batrinou, & Sflomos, 2009; Velasco, Ordóñez, Cambero, & Cabeza,
73 2015).

74 However, there are some discrepancies regarding the occurrence of off-odours and
75 depreciation of sensorial quality due to the application of ionizing radiation on dairy
76 foods (Odueke, Farag, Baines, & Chadd, 2016). Therefore, this work aimed to assess
77 the E-beam irradiation effect during storage on selected characteristics of hard
78 cheeses, namely, microbiota, physicochemical properties and colour, and textural and
79 sensory attributes. Since among hard varieties, Cheddar cheese is the most consumed
80 worldwide, this cheese type was used as a model in the present study.

81

82 **2. Material and methods**

83 **2.1. Experimental design**

84 The single and combined effects of ionizing radiation and storage conditions on
85 microbiota, colour and texture features and sensory properties were analysed using a
86 full factorial design (see factor levels in Table 1). For microbial analysis, samples were
87 taken based on the storage temperature until they reached 60, 40 and 20 days of
88 storage at 4, 10 and 14°C, respectively. Sampling at 0, 14 and 28 days of storage were
89 taken for instrumental (colour and texture) and sensory analysis. According to Bower
90 (2009), the full factorial design yielded 96, 72 and 24 experiments for microbial, colour,
91 and texture and sensory analysis, respectively.

92

93 **2.2. Sample preparation and irradiation treatment**

94 In an attempt to assess the effect of E-beam on the orange pigment, coloured cheese
95 samples were used. Whole cheeses labelled “Cheddar cheese” were purchased at a
96 local supermarket. Different size portions (experimental units) were made as

97 convenient (Table 1) using an electric machine (Beckers Italy, Treviglio, Italy), whose
98 contact surfaces were previously thoroughly cleaned and rinsed with sterile distilled
99 water. Experimental units were vacuum-packaged and transferred to the radiation plant
100 (Ionisos Ibérica, S.A., Tarancón, Spain). The treatment was performed in triplicate as
101 previously described (Velasco et al., 2015). In short, samples were irradiated under an
102 E-beam radiation source, which operates at 10 MeV. The radiation doses employed
103 were 0 (control), 1, 2 and 3 kGy, and the dose absorbed by the samples was checked
104 by cellulose triacetate dosimeters (ASTM, 2000). After treatment, the samples were
105 divided into batches and stored at 4 and 14°C; the latter is a usual temperature for the
106 ripening of whole cheeses, but this is temperature abuse for the storage of commercial
107 cheese portions. For the microbiota analysis, an additional batch was stored at 10°C as
108 an example of the ripening temperature for some hard cheeses.

109

110 **2.3. Physicochemical analysis**

111 The cheese composition was determined in untreated slices. Moisture content, ash and
112 protein were analysed according to the AOAC (1995). Fat content was determined as
113 described by Hanson & Olley (1963). Water activity (a_w) and pH were determined at
114 25°C using a Decagon CX1 hygrometer (Decagon Devices Inc., Pullman, USA) and a
115 Crison Digit-501 pH metre (Crison Instruments, Barcelona, Spain), respectively.

116

117 **2.4. Microbial analysis**

118 To determine the total viable counts (TVC), samples were weighed and homogenized
119 with 20 ml of a sterile saline solution in a stomacher bag, and the proper dilutions were
120 inoculated in a plate count agar (Difco, Detroit, USA) by the pour-plate method.
121 Colonies forming units (CFU) were enumerated with a digital colony counter (J.P.
122 Selecta, Barcelona, Spain).

123 Survival curves of the microorganism were obtained by plotting the log CFU/g against
124 the radiation dose. Decimal reduction doses (D-values) were calculated as the negative

125 reciprocal of the slope from the linear regression equation of survival curves. The TVC
126 growth curves were constructed according to the Baranyi model (Baranyi & Roberts,
127 1994) using the Excel add-in fitting curves, Dmfit.

128

129 **2.5. Texture analysis**

130 Texture profile analysis (TPA) parameters (hardness, springiness, adhesiveness,
131 cohesiveness) were determined using a TA.XT2i SMS Stable Micro Systems Texture
132 Analyser (Stable Microsystems Ltd., Surrey, England) with the Texture Expert
133 programme and according to Velasco, Ordóñez, Cabeza, Hoz, & Cambero (2011). At
134 least two cylindrical samples (1.5 cm height and 2 cm diameter) were taken from each
135 experimental unit (Table 1), i. e., for each combination of dose and storage time and
136 temperature, a value corresponding to the average of 6 measurements (2 replicates for
137 each treatment applied) was calculated.

138

139 **2.6. Colour analysis**

140 L^* (lightness), a^* (redness) and b^* (yellowness) parameters were measured by
141 duplicate samples on the surface of the experimental unit as reported in a previous
142 work (Velasco et al., 2011). As shown in Table 1, the colour parameters were
143 measured at different times after opening the pack (air exposure time, AET).

144

145 **2.7. Sensory analysis**

146 A triangular test was carried out to study the sensorial attributes (appearance, odour
147 and flavour) of the samples. According to the experimental design (Table 1), untreated
148 and irradiated portions were analysed as previously described (Velasco et al., 2011).
149 Moreover, panellists had to indicate which samples, if any, would be rejected because
150 of their defective sensory quality, justifying their answers with brief descriptions.

151

152 **2.8. Statistical analysis**

153 Statistical analyses of single-variable data (one-way and multifactor ANOVA and
154 Duncan's multiple range test) were performed using Statgraphics Centurion XVI
155 (Statistical Graphics Corporation, Rockville, USA).

156 The combined effect of the radiation dose and storage conditions on colour and texture
157 properties was analysed using a multivariate statistical procedure, including principal
158 component analysis (PCA) and hierarchical cluster analysis (HCA). These analyses
159 were performed with the programme SPAD.N, (Système Portable pour l'analyse des
160 données, CISIA, Montreuil Cedex, France). The raw data matrix was constructed with
161 the values measured in every experiment (Table 1). Texture and colour data were
162 scaled to unit variance to ensure that variables equally weighted the clustering
163 analysis. Principal components were calculated as linear combinations of the
164 standardized characteristics variables. The resulting PCA scores were the data inputs
165 in the HCA. The dissimilarity between scores was measured with the Euclidean
166 distance, and the hierarchical linkage Ward's method was used to group them, which
167 allowed for the determination of the appropriate number of clusters characterized by
168 the colour and texture variables that presented values above or below the global
169 average.

170

171 **3. Results and discussion**

172 **3.1. Physicochemical features**

173 The proximate cheese composition (mean±standard deviation) (g/100 g) was moisture
174 35.6±0.6, fat 35.6±2.5, protein 27.9±2.8 and ash 1.9±0.6. These results were within the
175 specifications for hard cheeses (FDA, 2016).

176 The a_w and pH values (Table 2) were similar to those found by Hickey, Guinee, Hou, &
177 Wilkinson (2013). No significant difference ($p>0.05$) in both parameters among the
178 control and irradiated samples were found, according to the observations of several
179 cheese varieties (Konteles et al., 2009; Velasco et al., 2011; Velasco et al., 2015). *L.*
180 *monocytogenes* is a bacterium able to grow at pH values of 4.0-4.4 and at a_w values of

181 0.90 (Lado & Yousef, 2007). In case of contamination with *L. monocytogenes*, the retail
182 samples (pH 5.58-5.61; a_w 0.953-0.958) of this kind of cheese did not meet the EU food
183 safety criterion of either 100 CFU/g (for food able to support the listerial growth) or in
184 absence of 25 g for those countries with a more restricted microbiological regulation,
185 such as the USA. It would be necessary, therefore, to take action to reduce the number
186 of *L. monocytogenes* until it is at a safe level. In the present manuscript, it is indicated
187 that E-beam treatment is a very useful tool to achieve this goal, which is supported by
188 several authors (Kim et al., 2007; Konteles et al., 2009; Velasco et al., 2015).

189

190 **3.2. Effect of E-beam treatment on microbiota**

191 The E-beam treatment caused a reduction in TVC of samples. The higher the dose that
192 was applied, the greater the reduction degree was. Control samples accounted for 7.91
193 log CFU/g at day 0, which decreased by 1.47, 3.91 and 5.87 log units when doses of 1,
194 2 and 3 kGy were applied, respectively. These data fitted first-order inactivation kinetics
195 ($R^2=0.99$), and a D-value of 0.5 kGy was calculated. Seisa et al. (2004) observed a
196 decrease of the TVC to approximately 3 log CFU/g in Cheddar cheese treated at 4
197 kGy. This lower reduction could be due to the M17 agar used by the authors since it is
198 a nutritious medium favourable for the growth of *Lactococcus* species (Terzaghi &
199 Sandine, 1975) and thus could promote a higher recovery of these bacteria.

200 Changes in the TVC during the storage at 4, 10 and 14°C are depicted in Figure 1.
201 While the control samples' counts were kept constant under the storage conditions
202 tested, the recovery of the irradiated microbiota depended on both the applied dose
203 and the storage temperature. The microbial population of samples treated with 1 kGy
204 returned to the initial levels, showing generation times (g values) of 2.19, 1.91 and 1.78
205 days during storage at 4, 10 and 14°C, respectively. As expected, the lag time
206 decreased with increased temperature at 19 and 5 days of storage at 4 and 10°C, and
207 no lag time was detected at 14°C. A similar pattern was exhibited for the TVC of
208 samples irradiated at 2 kGy, although the growth rate was slower, with g values of

209 2.31, 2.20 and 1.83 days, respectively, for the above-cited temperatures. No colonies
210 were detected in the samples subjected to 3 kGy and stored at 4 and 10°C, but at
211 14°C, the microbiota grew, reaching approximately 5 log CFU/g after 17 days of
212 storage and exhibiting a g value of 1.88 days. This microbiota behaviour has also been
213 observed by other authors in similar experiments (Seisa et al. 2004; Velasco et al.,
214 2011; Velasco et al., 2015). According to Daly (2012), the recovery of the irradiated
215 bacteria is dependent on the degree of DNA damage and the accumulation of oxidative
216 proteome harm caused by this treatment, which could compromise the enzymatic
217 activity for both the DNA repair and growth.

218

219 **3.3. Effect of E-beam treatment on cheese colour and texture**

220 Figure 2 shows changes in L^* , a^* and b^* parameters of untreated and irradiated (1-3
221 kGy) samples immediately after the E-beam treatment. Differences detected at day 0
222 and a few minutes of AET (0 h) could be solely attributed to the radiation effect. An
223 inverse relationship ($p < 0.05$) between the a^* values and the dose was observed,
224 ranging from 9.59 (control samples) to 6.51 (treated at 3 kGy samples). The b^*
225 parameter showed an increase from 44.45 in the untreated cheese to 45.60 in samples
226 subjected at 1 kGy, although a significant decrease ($p < 0.05$) was detected when higher
227 doses were applied. The red and yellow hues of these cheeses are related to the
228 content from the main pigments annatto bixin and norbixin, respectively (Smith, Li, &
229 Drake, 2014). The molecular structures of these oil- and water-soluble carotenoids
230 contain 9 conjugated double bonds (Cosentino, Takinami, & del Mastro, 2016), which
231 are the target of free radicals produced by water radiolysis (hydroxyl, OH^*). The loss of
232 redness and yellowness could be due, therefore, to bixin and norbixin oxidation
233 (Dufossé, Fernández-López, Galaup, & Pérez-Álvarez, 2015). The b^* value increase
234 when doses up to 2 kGy are applied, which was observed by Cosentino et al., (2016) in
235 water-solution annatto extracts treated with ionizing radiation, while higher doses (4-32
236 kGy) gave rise to a significant decrease of the yellowness. This behaviour was

237 attributed by the authors to the dual character of carotenoids as antioxidant or
238 prooxidant.

239 Regarding the AET effect on the untreated samples (Figure 2, dotted bars), the
240 lightness decreased gradually, and the samples became more reddish ($p < 0.05$). A
241 significant ($p < 0.05$) increase of b^* in the early 4 hours of AET was detected, followed
242 by a decrease until it reached the initial level at 24 hours of exposure. These changes
243 may be related to a higher concentration of annatto due to the slow decrease in
244 moisture content during storage (Petersen, Wiking, & Stapelfeldt, 1999). The colour
245 pattern of the irradiated cheese (1-3 kGy) during AET differed from that of the control
246 cheese, possibly due to the interaction of the E-beam treatment and exposure to air
247 (Figure 2). Therefore, the L^* value decrease in irradiated samples (1-3 kGy) was only
248 significant after 24 hours of AET. The a^* values were different, showing a general
249 increase immediately after the treatment and a decrease afterwards, during AET; the
250 higher the irradiation dose was, the smoother the variation. A similar trend for the a^*
251 parameter was observed for the b^* parameter. In summary, it appears that E-beam
252 treatment could attenuate the cheese discolouration when it is the cheese was
253 exposed to air.

254 Figure 3 shows the results of the TPA analysis for hardness and cohesiveness. A
255 hardness decrease ($p < 0.05$) was observed in irradiated cheese at 1, 2 and 3 kGy (from
256 74.54 N to 52.61, 59.31 and 54.86 N, respectively), although no significant differences
257 among treated samples were found. Cohesiveness also decreased ($p < 0.05$) with
258 irradiation at higher doses. No significant difference ($p > 0.05$) among the samples were
259 found in adhesiveness or springiness. These findings agree with previous work
260 (Velasco et al., 2011). The softening and loss of cohesiveness would be related to
261 either a decrease in protein-to-protein interactions and/or a shorter length of the protein
262 strands (Pastorino, Hansen, & McMahon, 2003) or changes in the peptide profiles by
263 irradiation (Seisa et al., 2004).

264 Initially, a multifactor ANOVA was performed to establish the significance of the effect
265 of irradiation dose (D), storage time (t) and temperature (T) and their interactions on
266 the colour and texture parameters (Figures S1, S2 and S3 of the supplementary
267 information). For hardness, springiness and colour parameters, the interaction of DxTxt
268 was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). Multifactor ANOVA for cohesiveness showed a
269 significant effect ($p < 0.05$) of the interactions Dxt and Txt. Neither the irradiation dose
270 nor the selected storage conditions significantly affected ($p > 0.05$) the adhesiveness of
271 cheese samples. However, these data were also included in the principal components
272 analysis (PCA) and hierarchical cluster analysis (HCA). The former statistical
273 procedure revealed that 82.4% of the total variance was explained by PC1 (38.93%),
274 PC2 (16.32%), PC3 (11.06%), PC4 (9.41%) and PC5 (6.72%) (Table S1). Since the
275 highest contributions corresponded to the two first principal components, PC1 and PC2
276 were used in scores plot (Figure 4).

277 According to clustering study, the PCA scores of the samples were grouped in three
278 different clusters, which could be characterized by the difference between the overall
279 mean value and the cluster mean for each studied parameter (Table 3). Cluster 1
280 represented 43% of the total samples and included the control samples (0 kGy) during
281 the storage period (0-28 days) at both temperatures and the samples irradiated at 1
282 kGy immediately after the treatment (day 0) and stored at 4°C (days 14 and 28) and
283 14°C (day 14). These samples showed a higher redness and yellowness during the
284 AET. Regarding texture features, only cohesiveness was significantly inferior to the
285 overall mean. Cluster 2 (42% of total samples) included the samples irradiated at
286 higher doses (2 and 3 kGy) immediately after the treatment (day 0) and those that were
287 stored at 4°C (14 and 28 days) and 14°C (14 days). Lightness at 4 hours of AET (L-4),
288 redness and yellowness of this cluster were lower than the overall mean. No significant
289 differences were found in the texture variables. Finally, Cluster 3 (15% of the samples)
290 included the irradiated cheese (1-3 kGy) at day 28 of storage at 14°C. Samples
291 displayed mean values of hardness and lightness (at 0, 4 and 24 hours of AET) above

292 the average, and cohesiveness, redness (a-0, a-4, a-24) and yellowness (b-0, b-4)
293 showed mean values below the overall average.

294 HCA revealed a differentiation among the samples according to the irradiation
295 treatment and the storage conditions. On the one hand, PC1 allowed for discrimination
296 between the samples treated at doses up to 1 kGy (cluster 1) from those irradiated at
297 higher doses, i.e., 2-3 kGy, (cluster 2), provided that they were maintained at a
298 refrigeration temperature (4°C) during at least the first 28 days of storage. On the other
299 hand, irradiation of cheese, even at doses from 1 kGy, caused greater changes in the
300 colour and texture characteristics when the temperature abuse occurred. PC1 and PC2
301 reflected the combined effect, being able to differentiate control samples (cluster 1)
302 from irradiated ones (cluster 3) after 28 days of storage at 14°C.

303

304 **3.4. Sensory analysis**

305 Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in odour, appearance and flavour obtained in the
306 triangular test and the overall acceptability of cheese stored at both temperatures are
307 provided in Tables 4 and 5, respectively. The control and irradiated samples were
308 significantly different ($p < 0.05$) immediately after the treatment (day 0). The irradiated
309 cheeses presented off-odours and off-flavours, which were described by the panellists
310 as burnt, rancid, plastic/rubber, and pungent. Similar descriptions have also been made
311 of irradiated cheeses by other authors (Seisa et al., 2004; Oudeke et al., 2016). The
312 differences among the irradiated samples (1-3 kGy) were dose-dependent. The higher
313 the dose applied, the greater the off-odours and off-flavour intensity. Consequently, the
314 percentage of questionable samples increased from 2 to 22% when treated at 1 and 3
315 kGy, respectively.

316 During storage at both temperatures, the off-odour and off-flavours associated
317 progressively decreased, such that the questionable sample percentage after 28 days
318 reached negligible values after doses of 1 and 2 kGy were used. Even at 3 kGy, an
319 important reduction (10-12%) was observed. This behaviour was due to the dissipation

320 of the sapid and aromatic volatile compounds. The reversibility of the odour and flavour
321 changes in irradiated cheeses has been reported by several authors (Konteles et al.,
322 2009; Seisa et al., 2004; Velasco et al., 2011). According to Konteles et al. (2009), the
323 oxidation phenomena of lipids and proteins produced by ionizing irradiation lead to
324 secondary oxidation products, which are responsible for off-odours that in turn undergo
325 polymerization or isomerisation reactions, thus giving rise to less volatile compounds.
326 The irradiated cheeses stored at 14°C were defined as less cohesive and with lower
327 moisture than the untreated cheeses. This texture change and the dissipation of the
328 sapid substances associated with radiolysis during storage time explained why no
329 significant differences in flavour of irradiated samples at different doses were detected
330 (Table 4).

331 At the end of storage (day 28), the control samples achieved a rejection percentage
332 (19-22%) higher than that of treated samples, irrespective of the dose, due to
333 development of off-odours and off-flavours related to spoilage (mouldy, cellar odours).
334 A preference order test reported for processed Cheddar slices subjected to gamma
335 irradiation (Kim et al., 2007) agreed with the results here obtained. However, it has also
336 been reported (Seisa et al., 2004) that the irradiation at 4 kGy of Cheddar cheese did
337 not lead to significant differences in the first days of ripening.

338 The triangular test showed that appearance was the most affected attribute by
339 irradiation treatment. The higher the irradiation dose was, the larger the changes in the
340 reddish colour of samples, which is in complete agreement with the behaviour
341 observed for the a^* parameter (Figure 2). However, in practice, commercial hard
342 cheese colour ranges from an intense orange to ivory-like tint (Codex Alimentarius,
343 2013). Furthermore, a widely sensorial quality of commercial Cheddar cheeses is
344 observed between different brands and between production batches belonging to the
345 same manufacturer (Guinee, Kilcawley, & Beresford, 2008). Therefore, it appears that
346 the sensory quality of these cheeses is not compromised by the application of
347 irradiation treatments up to 2 kGy.

348

349 4. Conclusions

350 The use of E-beam treatment at doses of up to 2 kGy in hard annatto-coloured cheese
351 leads to a decrease in the total bacterial number, although microbiota recovery to the
352 initial levels during storage is observed, even under refrigeration.

353 The effects of the dose treatment on the hardness, springiness, cohesiveness and
354 colour parameters are interdependent of the storage conditions. Although off-odour and
355 off-flavours may arise just after treatment, they disappear progressively during storage.
356 The redness and yellowness of annatto-coloured cheeses are reduced by the E-beam
357 treatment, however, the appearance of samples irradiated at doses up to 3 kGy
358 remains in the colour range of commercial orange cheeses.

359

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364

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483 **Figure captions**

484 Figure 1. Total viable counts of control (circles) and irradiated cheese samples at 1
485 (triangles), 2 (squares) and 3 kGy (diamonds) stored at 4°C (left), 10°C (central) and
486 14°C (right). No colonies were detected in samples treated with 3 kGy and stored at
487 both 4°C and 10°C, even for 60 and 40 days of storage, respectively.

488

489 Figure 2. The effect of irradiation dose (0–3 kGy) and air exposure time (AET 0, 4 and
490 24 h) on lightness (L^*), redness (a^*) and yellowness (b^*) of annatto-coloured cheese
491 samples immediately after the E-beam treatment (day 0).

492 a, b, c: bars with different letters within the same AET are significantly different
493 ($p < 0.05$).

494 α_x , β_x , γ_x : Different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$) during AET in
495 samples subjected at an irradiation dose of X kGy.

496

497 Figure 3. The effect of the irradiation dose (0–3 kGy) on the hardness and
498 cohesiveness of hard annatto-coloured cheese after the E-beam treatment.

499 a, b: Different letters indicate statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

500

501 Figure 4. The scores plot for the principal component analysis (PCA) of the textural and
502 colour features of the hard annatto-coloured cheese and clusters obtained by
503 hierarchical cluster analysis (HCA). The raw data were acquired in untreated and
504 irradiated (1-3 kGy) just after E-beam treatment (day 0) and at day 14 and 28 of
505 storage at 4 and 14°C.

506 The centroid and data of the cluster are represented by black circles (cluster 1), black
507 crosses (cluster 2) and black triangles (cluster 3). The mean points for the categories
508 of irradiation dose (grey squares), storage time (grey diamonds) and storage
509 temperature (grey pentagons) are also included. The arrow follows the sample

510 grouping tendency line obtained by linear regression of the score averages calculated
511 for each dose of the E-beam treatment.

ACCEPTED MANUSCRIPT

Table 1. Full factorial design followed in the analysis of the characteristic variables of the experiment.

Characteristics variables	Experimental unit (size, cm)	Design	Factor ^a			
			D (kGy)	T (°C)	time (day)	AET (h)
Microbiota Total viable counts	slice (3 x 3 x 0.2)	Level Factor values	4 x 0,1,2,3	3 x 4,10,14	8 x 0-60	1 x 0
Colour Lightness Redness Yellowness	block (5 x 10 x 1)	Level Factor values	4 x 0,1,2,3	2 x 4,14	3 x 0,14,28	3 x 0,4,24
Texture Hardness Cohesiveness Springiness Adhesiveness	block (10 x 10 x 1.5)	Level Factor values	4 x 0,1,2,3	2 x 4,14	3 x 0,14,28	1 x 0
Sensory analysis Odour Flavour Appearance Acceptability	slice (3 x 3 x 0.2)	Level Factor values	4 x 0,1,2,3	2 x 4,14	3 x 0,14,28	1 x 0

^a Factors D, T, time and AET denote irradiation dose (kGy), storage temperature (°C), storage time (day) and air exposure time (h), respectively.

- 1 Table 2. The water activity (a_w) and pH at 25 °C of the untreated and E-beam-irradiated
2 (1-3 kGy) hard cheese samples (mean \pm standard deviation)
3

Dose (kGy)	a_w	pH
0	0.953 \pm 0.007	5.58 \pm 0.06
1	0.953 \pm 0.003	5.62 \pm 0.01
2	0.958 \pm 0.002	5.62 \pm 0.01
3	0.958 \pm 0.001	5.61 \pm 0.02

4

Table 3. The study of the combined effects of the E-beam treatment and storage conditions (temperature and time) on colour and texture parameters of cheese by hierarchical cluster analysis (HCA)

Cluster	Variable	Cluster mean	Cluster SD	Overall mean	Overall SD	p-value
CLUSTER 1						
(43%)	a-0	9.08	0.92	7.74	1.46	***
	a-4	10.95	1.18	9.31	1.76	***
	a-24	11.41	1.61	9.57	2.01	***
	b-0	45.66	1.56	44.13	2.04	***
	b-4	49.33	1.54	47.45	2.19	***
	b-24	47.76	2.83	46.49	2.52	***
	Cohesiveness	0.21	0.04	0.19	0.04	***
	L-4	63.23	1.49	63.87	2.55	*
	L-24	60.82	2.07	62.54	3.18	***
CLUSTER 2						
(42%)	L-4	62.70	1.36	63.87	2.55	***
	a-0	6.88	0.74	7.74	1.46	***
	a-4	8.27	0.87	9.31	1.76	***
	a-24	8.28	0.60	9.57	2.01	***
	b-0	42.94	1.46	44.13	2.04	***
	b-4	46.47	1.16	47.45	2.19	***
	b-24	45.41	1.61	46.49	2.52	***
	CLUSTER 3					
(15%)	L-0	69.02	1.25	68.12	1.80	*
	L-4	68.95	0.95	63.87	2.55	***
	L-24	68.64	1.93	62.54	3.18	***
	Hardness	71.98	4.49	58.73	14.75	***
	b-0	43.09	1.76	44.13	2.04	*
	b-4	44.79	1.27	47.45	2.19	***
	a-0	6.30	0.99	7.74	1.46	***
	a-4	7.51	0.76	9.31	1.76	***
	a-24	7.89	1.14	9.57	2.01	***
	Cohesiveness	0.15	0.01	0.19	0.04	***

The mean values and standard deviation (SD) for each cluster against overall values.

L-x, a-x, b-x denote lightness, redness and yellowness after x hours of AET, respectively.

(%): Percentage of variability explained by the cluster

*** $p < 0.0001$; * $p < 0.01$

Table 4. The sensory characteristics of the untreated and irradiated hard cheese that showed significant differences ($p < 0.05$) in the triangular test after treatment (day 0) and 14 and 28 days of storage at 4 or 14°C.

Dose (kGy)	0	1	2	3
0		4°C $A_{0,14,28}; O_{0,28}; F_{0,28}$	4°C $A_{0,14,28}; O_{0,14,28}; F_{0,14,28}$	4°C $A_{0,14,28}; O_{0,14,28}; F_{0,14,28}$
1	14°C $A_{0,14,28}; O_{0,28}; F_{0,28}$		4°C $A_{0,14,28}; O_{0,14}; F_{0,14}$	4°C $A_{0,14,28}; O_{0,14,28}; F_{0,14,28}$
2	14°C $A_{0,14,28}; O_{0,14,28}; F_{0,14,28}$	14°C $A_{0,14,28}; O_{0,14}; F_{0,14}$		4°C $A_{0,14,28}; O_{0,28}; F_{14,28}$
3	14°C $A_{0,14,28}; O_{0,14,28}; F_{0,14,28}$	14°C $A_{0,14,28}; O_{0,14,28}; F_{0,14}$	14°C $A_{0,14,28}; O_{0,28}; F_{14}$	

A, O, F: Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) for appearance, odour and flavour, respectively.

Table 5. The overall acceptability of the untreated and irradiated hard cheese after treatment (day 0) and 14 and 28 days of storage at 4 or 14°C, expressed as percentage of panellists qualifying the samples as questionable.

Storage temperature (°C)	Storage time (day)	Irradiation dose			
		0 kGy	1 kGy	2 kGy	3 kGy
4	0	0	2	10	22
	14	0	1	6	18
	28	19	1	1	12
14	14	0	2	9	19
	28	22	0	2	10

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

a, b: Different letters indicate statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 4

Highlights:

- Microbiota of cheese treated up to 2 kGy reach initial levels during storage at 4°C
- Orange cheese discolouration due to air exposure is attenuated by E-beam radiation
- Colour and texture changes depend on both, dose and storage conditions
- E-beam treatment does not compromise the sensory quality of hard cheeses